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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN INTERACTIVE MATERIAL IN SCIENCE 7

A Thesis Presented to the
Faculty of College of Education
Center of Development in Education
Graduate School Program
Tarlac State University
Tarlac City

In Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements for the Degree
Master of Arts in Education
Major in Physical Science

ALEAH G. SABADO
Author

RITA E. PULMANO, Ed.D.
Co-Author

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on developing and validating an Interactive Material for Grade 7 Students to improve students' learning achievements such as process skills, content knowledge, problem-solving, and learning outcomes. The researcher used research and development design in developing the Interactive Material while the Department of Education's LRMSD Evaluation Tool for Non-Print Materials was utilized to determine the validity of the interactive material in terms of content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and errors wherein the evaluators were Science and IT experts. After the evaluation, the 52 Grade 7 participants utilized the developed Interactive material and validated its effectiveness based on their pretest and posttest results.

The research findings revealed that the developed interactive material was found to be very satisfactory and passed all the criteria in terms of content quality and instructional quality both having 39.75 points, technical quality with the maximum of 52 points, and other findings getting the maximum of 16 points which complied with the minimum requirements set by the Department of Education. Therefore, the Interactive Material was found valid and recommended by the evaluators to be utilized in teaching and learning topics in Chemistry 7. Furthermore, the result of the paired samples t-test showed that there was a significant difference between the participants' pretest with a mean rating of 13.8, and posttest scores with a mean rating of 38.6. In summary, there was a mean difference of 24.8 and a sig. (2-tailed) of <0.001, in the pretest – posttest performance of the student participants.

Therefore, there was a remarkable improvement in the student's performance when they utilized the developed Interactive Material which may be used as an additional learning resource in teaching Chemistry to Grade 7 students. This would also help the Department of Education authorities, school administrators, teachers, and all people in the community to have a continuing and quality education by having diverse learning resource material.

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INTRODUCTION

Science enhances critical thinking, problem-solving, and innovation and helps people understand the world. The K to 12 Science Curriculum Guide of the Department of Education (2016) states that science education aims to establish scientifically literate citizens who can use scientific knowledge to make judgments and decisions that can have an impact on our society, health, and environment. However, the poor level of scientific literacy among Filipino students makes it difficult to attain this objective. According to studies from Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2019 and the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2022, Filipino students continue to have the lowest rankings, particularly in the area of science.

In connection to this, low performance in Science was also observed among the students at Rodolfo V. Feliciano Memorial High School where the study was conducted. Based on the available data, the average Mean Percentage Score (MPS) of Science for four consecutive school years (S.Y. 2018-2022) is only 63.40%. While on the Regional Diagnostic Assessment taken last school year 2022-2023, the Grade 7 students only got 6.41%.

Grade 7 is a crucial time in education for the students as they enter the high school learning environment. They need to adapt to a new learning environment where they are treated differently from the primary school level. During this time, students must develop analytical thinking, decent knowledge, and a positive attitude toward science learning that would develop related skills in education that could shape their future careers (Afari, 2019).

In the first quarter of Science 7, the branch of Science to start with is Chemistry which the students generally perceived as difficult. In learning complex subjects like Chemistry, the acquisition of a basic understanding of the subject upon more complex learning is necessary. Appropriate learning materials that help students learn the basic knowledge of the subject should always be considered.

As stated in one of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, which aims to ensure inclusive quality education and encourage continuous and lifelong learning opportunities for all. The world needs to secure equitable and accessible quality education, aiming for relevant and operative learning outcomes. However, the United Nations (2021) reported that the progress in education is too slow in achieving SDG 4. One of the significant problems in the current situation is that internet service, computers, and other necessary technologies in schools are scarce enough to support the teaching and varied learning processes.

Interactive learning materials are interactive resources crafted to teach a specific learning outcome. They include a combination of text, images, audio, videos, or animations. Interactive learning materials increase engagement since the students involve multiple senses at once and ensure that students have a baseline knowledge of particular subjects. They are beneficial in the teaching-learning process for they offer a multi-sensory approach to learning making it more engaging and making the students active learners.

However, one of its drawbacks is the need for internet connectivity in using them which is inefficient in the Philippines. Technology issues like internet connectivity are one of the problems which teachers and students alike are facing. Therefore, the

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development of an interactive yet offline learning material is important to help students learn basic concepts in Chemistry like Matter. In the study of Abante et al. (2021), revealed that both public and private school teachers from Bulacan and Pampanga experienced problems with internet connectivity during online and modular learning modalities.

The findings of the study conducted by Anwar et al. (2020) showed that the developed interactive video-based PowerPoint media to teach Mathematics at Quba Sorong Middle School Class VII in Indonesia was valid, useful, and effective. Students passed the presentation effectiveness test with an average score of 70.29% following the use of the interactive PowerPoint.

Hence, the researcher aimed to develop a PowerPoint-based interactive learning material in Science 7. This offline interactive learning material had text, images, and games that were engaging and helped the Grade 7 students acquire basic knowledge relating to specific lessons in Matter which they applied in learning complex concepts of Chemistry as they proceeded to a higher-grade level. The learning competencies were taken in the 1st quarter under the field of Chemistry from the K to 12 Science curriculum guide. Furthermore, the developed interactive material can be utilized by Science teachers to make their classes more engaging and student-centered. This served as an additional resource for the teachers and students to understand the lessons and themes with the most crucial learning competencies to significantly increase students' subject-matter understanding and students' achievement in Science and realize the goal of Science education in making scientifically literate citizens.

Statement of Objectives

Generally, this study aimed to develop and validate an Interactive Material in Chemistry for Grade 7 students.

Specifically, it achieved the following research objectives:

1. Develop an Interactive Material for Grade 7 students.
2. Validate the developed Interactive Material by:
 - 2.1 Science and IT experts in the areas of:
 - 2.1.1. Content Quality;
 - 2.1.2. Instructional Quality;
 - 2.1.3. Technical Quality; and
 - 2.1.4. Other Findings
 - 2.2. Users
 - 2.2.1 Effectiveness (Pretest & Posttest)
3. Compare the difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the student participants.

Hypothesis of the Study

H₀: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

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This study utilized a Research and Development (R&D) method. According to Tarver (2015), the research portion is the act of discovering new ways that can be used to create new products or resources. The development comes after the research has been conducted and is the act of turning it into a useful product whether technological, educational, or others. The researcher used this method since this study aims to develop an interactive material as a learning resource in teaching Chemistry for Grade 7 science to be validated by the students, Science Teachers, and IT Experts.

Furthermore, this study also used a One-Group Pretest-Posttest Design to evaluate the validity and effectiveness of the developed interactive material. According to Choueiry (2023), this is a type of quasi-experiment in which the outcome of interest is measured 2 times: once before (pretest) and once after (posttest) exposing a non-random group of participants to a certain intervention/treatment. It is one way to minimize problems of having no control or comparison group to measure the same dependent variable and then compare the difference between the pretest and posttest scores of one group of participants.

Participants of the Study

The study involved three groups of participants which have a significant role in the study to answer each research question. An informed consent form was given before the participation of the respondents. The experts and student participants were chosen through purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a non-probability method for obtaining a sample where researchers use their expertise to choose specific participants that will help the study meet its goals. The subjects have particular characteristics that the researchers need to evaluate their research question (Frost, 2021).

The first group of participants was composed of eight (8) expert validators in evaluating the developed interactive material. It was evaluated by three (3) Science teachers, one (1) Master teacher in Science, two (2) Associate Professors, and two (2) Information and Technology experts. The validators were experts and knowledgeable in the field of teaching with a Master's degree and some with a Doctoral degree in Science Education while the Information and Technology experts were adept in integrating technology into education and were currently teaching in a University with a Master's degree in their field of expertise.

Meanwhile, the researcher utilized a 50-item teacher-made test anchored to the 1st quarter topics in Science 7 under the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum Guide. The second group of participants consisted of fifty (50) Grade 7 students from Rodolfo V. Feliciano High School in Magalang, Pampanga took pilot testing of the material. The pretest-posttest material underwent item analysis to determine the difficulty index and discrimination index of each item. The participants were chosen through the purposive sampling method.

Lastly, the interactive material underwent implementation to determine its effectiveness by the third group of participants in another section consisting of fifty-two (52) Grade 7 students handled by the researcher. The interactive material was utilized during the teaching and learning process as well as all of the participants accessed it on their own devices.

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Research Instruments

The researcher adopted and utilized the Department of Education (DepEd) LRMS Rating Sheet for Non-Print Materials as a tool for evaluating the interactive material. This Evaluation Rating sheet is guided and based on the Learning Resource Management and Development System of the Department of Education which provides access to quality resources from the Regions, Divisions, and Cluster/School Level. The first part includes information about the developed interactive material in Chemistry for Grade 7. The second part is divided into four (4) different factors namely: content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and other findings. The evaluation tool has a criteria frame of four (4) point Likert scale namely: (4) very satisfactory; (3) satisfactory; (2) poor; and (1) not satisfactory. The third part of the evaluation sheet is composed of the comment section for giving feedback and recommendations for the improvement and revision of the interactive material. The data that will be gathered from the validators in the interactive material will be the basis for the validity and reliability of the learning material if it can be used in the teaching of Chemistry in Grade 7.

Data Gathering Procedure

Development Phase

The contents of the interactive material were interactive lessons, video tutorials, and assessment tools which followed the process of the Research and Development procedures. After reading all the related literature, the researcher included the most essential learning competencies in Chemistry in Science 7 which became the basis for crafting the interactive lessons, video tutorials, and assessment tools. The objectives of the lessons included in the said materials were anchored on the competencies included in the Grade 7 Science Curriculum Guide. The interactive lessons covered the topics in the first quarter of Science 7: Unit 1 Diversity of Materials in the Environment; Lesson 1: Pure Substances and Mixtures, Lesson 2: Solutions, Lesson 3: Elements and Compounds, Lesson 4: Metals and Non Metals, and Lesson 5: Acid and Bases. The elements of the interactive lessons were composed of graphics, images, animations, and interactive texts to enhance the learning of the students. The researcher mostly used Canva for the Design of the elements and PowerPoint presentation for the layout. Meanwhile, the video tutorials are composed of video clips in MP4 file format which showed sample tutorials from the given experiments with instructions that used localized materials for a better understanding of the lessons. The game-based assessment and worksheet were given for each lesson for a more interactive evaluation. Lastly, comments and suggestions were collected from the validators to improve and finalize the developed interactive material.

Validation Phase

In the validation phase, the developed interactive material was reviewed and validated by the Science experts, and IT experts whose expertise was relevant to the field of Science education and technology. First, the researcher gave a letter of request to the validators which indicated the conduct of the study. The evaluation sheet was administered to the validators personally which determined the acceptability of the interactive material. Having said that, all the recommendations, reviews, comments,

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and suggestions of the experts were collected and incorporated into the interactive material and its contents for the revision of the material to make it more appropriate for the intended learners.

Administration of the Pretest and Posttest

The researcher sought permission through a letter from the school head of the school to allow the conduct of the experiment. The researcher also sought approval from the adviser and evaluators to conduct the administration of the interactive material as an additional learning resource. A 50-item teacher-made test questionnaire was administered to the first group of participants to assess its acceptability. Once done, the pretest was given to the 2nd group of participants which was composed of fifty-two (52) Grade 7 students in another section. Their level of learning was determined based on the scores that were collected from the pretest.

The researcher provided the interactive material as an additional learning resource for the teacher and the Grade 7 students. Afterward, the same test was conducted to identify the results of the applied interactive material in studying Chemistry. The posttest determined the mastered learning competencies of the participants after the utilization of the interactive material.

Data Analysis

After the conduct of the test, the researcher proceeded with the final evaluation. The data from the pre-test and post-test scores of the participants were collected, tallied, tabulated, and subjected to statistical treatment to get the mean scores of the development and validation of the interactive material in Chemistry for Science Grade 7.

1. Expert's Evaluation

Mean and Standard Deviation were computed to verify the expert's results. The mean provided a summary measure of the average evaluation of the experts. While standard deviation was calculated to get the variability or dispersion of scores around the mean. A smaller standard deviation indicates less variability (scores are close together), while a larger standard deviation indicates greater variability.

2. User's Evaluation

A paired sample t-test was used to identify the difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants where the interactive material was employed in the enhancement program. After the comparison between the pretest and posttest scores, the hypothesis was determined, if it was accepted or rejected.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

1. Validation of the Developed Interactive Material for Grade 7 Students

1.1 Experts

1.1.1. Content Quality

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Table 1. Mean Rating of Experts' Evaluation in Terms of Content Quality

Criteria for the Content Quality	Mean \pm SD	Descriptive Rating
Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Content is accurate	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Content is up-to-date	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Content is logically developed and organized.	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.88 \pm 0.35	Very Satisfactory
Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.88 \pm 0.35	Very Satisfactory
Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	4.00 \pm 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	3.98 \pm 0.71	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4 - Very Satisfactory; 3 - Satisfactory; 2 - Poor; 1 - Not Satisfactory

Table 1 shows the evaluation of the Science experts on the developed Interactive Material in Chemistry 7 in terms of content quality. It was rated as very satisfactory with an overall mean of 3.98. The content of the developed interactive material obtained a mean rating of 4.00 and was found very satisfactory on its consistency with the topics in the DepEd Learning Competency, contribution in the reinforcement or mastery of the learning objectives, accuracy, enrichment, up-to-date information, organization, unbiasedness from cultural, gender, racial or ethical, language appropriateness to the user, and promotion of positive values that support formative growth based on the experts' evaluation.

Meanwhile, a mean rating of 3.88 and was found very satisfactory both on its stimulation and promotion of critical thinking skills, and relevance to real-life situations. Based on the evaluation, improvements to the questions have been made to make the students think critically and analyze real-life situations. This means that the content quality of the developed interactive material is passed based on the criteria given.

2.1.2. Instructional Quality

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Table 2. *Mean Rating of Experts' Evaluation in Terms of Instructional Quality*

Criteria for the Instructional Quality	Mean ± SD	Descriptive Rating
The purpose of the material is well-defined.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Material achieves its defined purpose.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
The level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Graphics/colors/sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.88 ± 0.35	Very Satisfactory
The material effectively stimulates the creativity of the target user.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Feedback on the target user's responses is effectively employed.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Target users can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Instruction is integrated with the target user's previous experience.	3.88 ± 0.35	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	3.98 ± 0.46	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4 - Very Satisfactory; 3 - Satisfactory; 2 - Poor; 1 - Not Satisfactory

Table 2 shows the evaluation of the Science experts on the developed Interactive Material in Chemistry 7 in terms of instructional quality. It was rated with an overall rating of 3.98 which indicates that its instructional quality was very satisfactory. The developed interactive material obtained a mean rating of 4.00 and found very satisfactory on its well-defined purpose, achievement of the defined purpose, clarity and measurability of the learning objectives, appropriateness to the level of difficulty for the intended target users, appropriateness of the graphics, colors, and sounds used, ability to stimulate creativity, effective employment of feedback to user's response, and self-paced presentation and review. It obtained a mean rating of 3.88 and was found very satisfactory both on its ability to entertain, challenge, engage, and integrate of target user's previous experience. Based on the evaluation, the researcher improved the interactive material by making it more engaging and challenging to the users while integrating the science topics. This means that the instructional quality of the developed interactive material passed the criteria given.

2.1.3. Technical Quality

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Table 3. Mean Rating of Experts' Evaluation in Terms of Technical Quality

Criteria for the Technical Quality	Mean ± SD	Descriptive Rating
Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) are clear and can be easily understood.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Visuals sustain interest and do not distract the user's attention.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Visuals provide an accurate representation of the concept discussed.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
The user support materials (if any) are effective.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
The material can easily and independently be used.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
The material will run using minimum system requirements.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
The program is free from technical problems.	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	4.00 ± 0.00	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4 - Very Satisfactory; 3 - Satisfactory; 2 - Poor; 1 - Not Satisfactory

Table 3 shows the evaluation of the IT experts on the developed Interactive Material in Chemistry 7 in terms of technical quality. The developed interactive material obtained a mean rating of 4.00 and was found very satisfactory on the ability of its audio to better understand the concept, speech and narration were clear and easily understood, and complete synchronization of audio with the visual, appropriate, and effective use of music and audio, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing screen displays, which is easier to interpret when it comes to visuals, effective user support material, easy navigation design for the target user, easy and independent use, minimum system requirements, and free from technical problems. Overall, the interactive material is clear and user-friendly for the students. The inclusion of text, graphics, audio, video, and animations enhance the teaching and learning process.

2.1.4. Other Findings

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Table 4. Mean Rating of Experts' Evaluation in Terms of Other Findings

Criteria for Other Findings	Mean ± SD	Descriptive Rating
Conceptual errors.	4.00 ± 0.00	Not Present
Factual errors.	4.00 ± 0.00	Not Present
Grammatical and/or typographical errors.	4.00 ± 0.00	Not Present
Other errors (i.e., computational errors, obsolete information, errors in the visuals, etc.).	4.00 ± 0.00	Not Present
Overall	4.00 ± 0.00	Not Present

Legend: 4 - Not present; 3 - Present but very minor & must be fixed; 2 - Present & requires major redevelopment; 1 - Do not evaluate further

Table 4 shows the evaluation of the experts on the developed Interactive Material in Diversity of Materials in the Environment in terms of errors. The developed interactive material obtained a mean rating of 4.00 and found no errors in its concept, facts, grammar, typography, computation, and visuals. This signifies a high level of satisfaction among all the evaluators as they found no technical errors in the interactive material giving an overall mean of 4.00 under this factor.

Table 5. Summary of Mean Ratings from the Experts' Evaluation on the Interactive Material

Factors	Sum of Ratings Garnered	Min. and Max. Points	Remarks
Content Quality	39.75	Min: 30.00 Max: 40.00	Passed
Instructional Quality	39.75	Min: 30.00 Max: 40.00	Passed
Technical Quality	52.00	Min: 39.00 Max: 52.00	Passed
Other Findings	16.00	Min: 16.00 Max: 16.00	Passed

Table 5 shows the sum of the ratings per factor in evaluating the interactive material in science 7. The ratings garnered were compared to the minimum points required to pass each factor. Both the content and instructional quality gained 39.75 points while technical quality and other findings got the maximum required points. The minimum points required per factor are set by the Department of Education as indicated in the evaluation tools. If the sum of ratings from the evaluators meets the minimum rating required, the material will pass the specified factor. Otherwise, the material will be marked as failed and for revision if the material does not reach the minimum points needed.

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Overall, the developed Interactive Material in Science 7 was found to be very satisfactory in terms of content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and other findings. This was found valid and recommended by the evaluators to be used in teaching and learning topics under Diversity of Materials in the Environment. This conforms to the study conducted by Anwar et al. (2020) that the developed interactive video-based PowerPoint media for teaching Mathematics was valid, useful, and effective.

2.2 Users

Table 6. Paired Sample t-test between the Pretest-Posttest Performance of Student Participants

	Mean	SD	SE	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Description
Pretest	13.8	3.27	0.453	51.0	< .001	Reject the null hypothesis
Posttest	38.6	5.60	0.776			

The Grade 7 student participants' pretest and post-test comparisons demonstrated the value of the newly created interactive material in Chemistry 7. Using the paired sample t-test, the post-test mean (38.6) is significantly higher than the pretest mean (13.8) recorded. With a mean difference of 24.8 and a sig. (2-tailed) of <0.001, the t-test significantly differentiated the performance of the student participants in their pretest and post-test. This matches on the alpha level of 5%, wherein if the p-value (probability value) associated with a statistical test shows less than 0.05, it indicates that the result is statistically significant. This means there's less than a 5% chance of obtaining such a result if the null hypothesis is true, leading researchers to reject the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative hypothesis.

Conclusions

1. The Science and IT experts found the developed Interactive Material in Science 7 to be very satisfactory in terms of content quality, instructional quality, technical quality and other findings.
2. The utilization of the interactive material has demonstrated a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants.
3. The interactive material significantly improved students' academic performance, learners could identify, comprehend, and integrate the lessons learned. It has proven to be an effective approach to have a dynamic and multimedia-rich learning environment.

Recommendations

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1. Since the effectiveness of Interactive Material in science has been proven, teachers should incorporate this material into their classes to maintain the continuity of quality education through other modes of learning delivery.
2. In the development of another interactive material, developers should incorporate real-world applications of the topics that must be culturally and locally relevant to the community.
3. School administrators should support the implementation of interactive materials to continuously improve the quality of basic education.
4. An interactive material in other learning areas is encouraged and similar studies must be conducted on a large group of students to determine if the same conclusions will be drawn.

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